

GRAPHITE REINFORCED NONEQUILIBRIUM AL-MO METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Barbara A. Shaw ¹, William C. Moshier ², Robert G. Wendt ³

¹ *Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics, The Pennsylvania State University,
211 Hallowell Bldg., University Park, PA 16802, USA*

² *Global Solar Energy Incorporated, 12401 West 49th Avenue, Wheat Ridge, CO 80033, USA*

³ *Bettis Atomic Power Lab, PO Box 79, West Mifflin, PA 15122, USA*

SUMMARY: Poor corrosion resistance, fiber/matrix reaction-induced embrittlement, excessive thermal/strain hysteresis, and restricted processing capabilities are problems associated with graphite/aluminum MMCs. To alleviate these problems, this research investigated nonequilibrium alloying by sputter disposition.

Binary nonequilibrium Al-Cr, Al-Mo, Al-Ta, and Al-W alloys were successfully fabricated and evaluated. All Al-based alloys exhibited improved corrosion resistance over pure Al; Al-W and Al-Mo alloys showed marked increased resistance to pitting and galvanic corrosion.

An Al-17Mo alloy with pure Al surface foils and interlayers was chosen for processing into a composite. The best hot-pressed composites contained void contents exceeding 9% and processing damage of the Al surface foils exposed graphite fibers. SEM analysis of the pitted composite after anodic polarization in 0.1M NaCl revealed that diffusion bonding of the alloy coated fibers was not achieved; moreover, the alloy coating on the graphite fibers was apparently unchanged during diffusion bonding or polarization. The lack of diffusion bonding was disappointing, but the fact that the alloy coated fibers underwent no discernible degradation after polarization was very promising. An alternative consolidation approach, such as hot isostatic pressing without surface foils or using Al-Mo surface foils, could result in a fully consolidated, corrosion resistant composite.

KEYWORDS: graphite-reinforced metal matrix composites, nonequilibrium Al alloys, Al-based metal matrix composites, corrosion resistant composites

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been intensively studied over the past thirty years due to their unique combination of stiffness and thermal stability. During this period, there have been many proposals to develop matrix alloys that are compatible with the reinforcing phase. However, for one reason or another, the technology has continued to focus on conventional alloys and fabrication practices. Although there have been tremendous advances in the field of composite materials, the basic technology remains similar to systems studied twenty years ago. This work represents the first program where new alloys are being developed for graphite reinforced composites that are tailored to a novel processing technology for manufacturing corrosion resistant graphite reinforced composites.

Graphite fiber reinforced aluminum metal matrix composites are susceptible to rapid

corrosion especially in chloride environments [1-16], which has, in part, limited the use of these materials in aircraft, spacecraft, and naval applications. Attempts have been made to improve the corrosion resistance of graphite/aluminum composites through the use of coatings or some other form of electrical isolation between the fiber and matrix [4,5,7,9], cathodic protection, or cathodic inhibitors [3,13]. However, each of these protection techniques often adversely affects composite properties and in the long term only delays pitting and subsequent galvanic interaction between the matrix and fiber. In addition, none of these corrosion prevention processes address the real problem -- poor corrosion resistance of the aluminum matrix, especially when coupled to graphite fibers in a chloride-containing environment. In this program, the approach was to develop a corrosion resistant matrix alloy more electrochemically compatible with graphite than pure Al or commercially available Al alloys.

One study of the corrosion of graphite/aluminum MMCs reported that these composites corroded at rates up to fifteen times greater than monolithic aluminum alloys in a sodium chloride (NaCl) electrolyte at room temperature [13]. Corrosion of conventionally processed graphite/aluminum composites is a result of pitting of the face sheet foils. Once these foils have been penetrated, corrosion is accelerated by the following mechanisms [4,5,13-16]:

- Residual microstructural chlorides within the composite at precursor wire interfaces increase and lead to rapid internal composite corrosion, and
- Exposure of the graphite fibers creates a galvanic couple with the aluminum matrix leading to rapid matrix dissolution.

One of the key problems leading to rapid corrosion of graphite/aluminum composites stems from the current state-of-the-art (SOA) manufacturing of graphite/aluminum MMCs, which introduces residual microstructural chlorides during the liquid metal infiltration (LMI) process [13,17-21].

A new process has been developed, and is in commercial practice, that does not rely on the titanium diboride coating or the cast aluminum matrix [21,22]. In this process, the matrix alloy is deposited onto each individual fiber by a physical vapor deposition (PVD) method such as sputtering. The very nature of the PVD process allows virtually any matrix alloy to be deposited on the graphite fibers.

Using the PVD approach, composite processing involves the following steps:

- Deposit metal alloy onto fibers using automated magnetron sputtering (a process developed at Naval Research Laboratory and now in commercial practice).
- Configure the flexible graphite fibers by automated processes such as filament winding, braiding, or weaving.
- Consolidate the composite by low temperature diffusion bonding or hot isostatic pressing (HIPing).

Sputtering of metal alloys onto graphite fibers has several potential advantages over the current liquid metal infiltration process used to fabricate graphite/aluminum composites. The three most significant advantages of the physical vapor deposition method of fabricating graphite/aluminum composites are that it eliminates unwanted reactions at the fiber/matrix interface [23-30], it minimizes thermal strain hysteresis [21], and sputter coated graphite fibers provide near-net shape processing capability.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Non-equilibrium Al-Mo, Al-W, Al-Cr, and Al-Ta alloys for the initial phases of the investigation were prepared by co-sputtering the two elements onto silicon single crystal wafers using a Denton Vacuum 602RS Loadlock Thin Film Deposition System. For the final phase of the investigation, a nonequilibrium Al-17 atomic % (a/o%) Mo alloy was deposited onto graphite fibers using a proprietary process developed at Cordec Incorporated. The temperature of the substrates was not controlled during deposition for either of the substrates.

Compositional analysis of the alloys was conducted using the inductively coupled plasma (ICP) technique. Alloy compositions reported in this paper as Al-xxMo correspond to Al alloys with a Mo concentration, in atomic percent, of xx percent. X-ray diffraction (XRD) of each alloy film was conducted to determine: 1) whether the solute was in solid solution in the aluminum, and 2) whether precipitation occurred after heat treating. In the initial phases of the research, the alloy coated Si wafers were heat treated at 400, 500 and 600° C for times of one, two and eight hours to assess stability of the alloys at anticipated processing temperatures.

In the initial phases of the research, anodic polarization experiments were conducted to assess the corrosion resistance of each of the alloys in chloride-containing environments (typically 0.1M NaCl) before and after heat treatment. Corrosion testing during the initial phases of the investigation also included galvanic corrosion experiments. In these experiments, the alloy coated Si substrates were coupled to graphite-fiber specimens in 0.1M NaCl solutions and the galvanic corrosion current was monitored as a function of time. Later phases of the research involved anodic polarization testing of single alloy coated fibers and consolidated composites in chloride solutions. In all of the anodic potentiodynamic polarization experiments, the alloys were allowed to stabilize for at least one hour prior to scanning the potential at a rate of 0.2 mV/s, or lower. Areas not to be tested on electrochemical specimens were masked with a room temperature curing marine epoxy paint. All electrochemical tests were conducted under ambient lab conditions in cells open to the atmosphere and potentials were measured versus a saturated calomel electrode (SCE).

RESULTS

Alloy Development Studies

In comparison to pure Al and commercial Al alloys, all of the alloys investigated in this study exhibited enhanced corrosion resistance. Figure 1 shows a comparison of representative anodic polarization curves for four of the alloys produced in this study to that of pure Al. The largest passive regions were noted for the Al-W and Al-Mo alloys. X-ray diffraction of as-deposited Al-Mo, Al-W, Al-Cr and Al-Ta alloy films revealed that the solute in all of the alloys was in solid solution with the Al (i.e., no precipitates were found). After heat treatment at 400° C only the Al-Mo and Al-W alloys remained precipitate free. The lack of precipitation in the Al-Mo and Al-W alloy systems, especially at the higher solute concentrations despite the high driving force for precipitation, was believed to be a result of the amorphous nature of these alloys. This early segment of the investigation clearly showed that the Al-W and the Al-Mo alloy systems provided the best combination of corrosion resistance and thermal stability at anticipated processing temperatures.

Since one of the possible applications for MMCs made with these nonequilibrium alloys is aerospace structures, alloy density was an important parameter in selecting the best alloy for use in subsequent phases of the investigation. Because of their combination of corrosion

resistance, thermal stability, and density, the Al-Mo alloy system was selected for further evaluation and optimization. The following are important factors in determining the optimal Al-Mo alloy composition: lack of precipitates and the presence of a nanocrystalline/amorphous structure for the alloy after heat treatment at anticipated consolidation temperatures; extent of the passive region in alloy anodic polarization curve; galvanic compatibility of the alloy with graphite; corrosion resistance of the alloy after heat treatment at anticipated consolidation temperatures; and alloy density.

Fig. 1: Comparison of the anodic polarization behavior for the highest solute concentration Al nonequilibrium alloys in 0.1M NaCl under quiescent conditions.

X-ray Diffraction Studies

X-ray diffraction was conducted on both the as-sputtered and heat treated Al-Mo alloys to determine whether the Mo: 1) was in solid solution with the Al and readily available for enhancing corrosion resistance, or 2) had reacted with the Al to form Al_xMo_y precipitates. The as-deposited alloys showed no signs of precipitation. X-ray diffraction results for the heat-treated alloys are presented in Table 1. At the two higher Mo concentrations, the Al-Mo alloys exhibited no precipitates and a nanocrystalline/amorphous structure when heat treated at 400° C. Again, the lack of precipitation at the higher solute concentrations, despite the higher driving force for precipitation, was believed to be a result of the amorphous structure of the alloys.

Corrosion Evaluation

As Figure 1 revealed, the Al-Mo alloys exhibited significant passivity. This passivity was maintained in a variety of different chloride solutions over a wide range of pH and after galvanic coupling to either graphite, SiC, or TiB₂. A galvanic diagram for the Al-18Mo alloy coupled to various reinforcing materials in a variety of different chloride solutions is presented in Figure 2. This figure reveals that galvanic corrosion is controlled by the anodic metal dissolution reaction for the alloy rather than by the reduction of oxygen on the reinforcement material. Since the Al-18Mo alloy is passive in the crossover region for the two curves, low galvanic corrosion rates are predicted when this alloy is coupled to graphite. Current measurements in actual galvanic couple experiments, Figure 3, confirmed the galvanic diagram prediction and showed that low galvanic currents were also obtained after heat treatment of the alloy.

Table 1: Summary of Al-Mo Alloy structure as a function of heat treatment time and temperature

		Heat Treatment Temperature		
		400°C	500°C	600°C
Heat Treatment Time (h)	1	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, Amorphous Al-23Mo, Amorphous	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, ppt Al-23Mo, Amorphous	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, ppt Al-23Mo, Amorphous
	2	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, Amorphous Al-23Mo, Amorphous	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, ppt Al-23Mo, Amorphous	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, ppt Al-23Mo, Amorphous
	8	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, Amorphous Al-23Mo, Amorphous	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, ppt Al-23Mo, Amorphous	Al-11Mo, ppt Al-18Mo, ppt Al-23Mo, ppt

Fig. 2: Galvanic diagram created by overlaying the anodic polarization data for the Al-18 Mo alloy tested in quiescent 0.1M and 0.55M NaCl on the cathodic curves for P75 graphite, P100 graphite, SiC, and TiB₂. Cathodic data for P100 graphite, SiC and TiB₂ after Hihara and Latanision (16).

Coated Fiber Evaluation

Al with a Mo concentration greater than 11a/o Mo and less than, or equal to, 18 a/o Mo was targeted as the optimum alloy composition because these alloys showed promise for consolidation, they retained their enhanced corrosion resistance after heat treatment, and they minimized the impact of higher Mo concentrations on alloy density. Several fiber coating trials were conducted at Cordec Incorporated using a commercial in-line sputtering system designed for rapid deposition of alloys onto graphite fibers. Targets for this system were fabricated by inserting 99.9 % pure Mo plugs into 99.99 % pure Al plates. Alloy composition was controlled by modifying the area ratio of the Mo and Al. Both hollow cathode and planar cathode sputter deposition processes were investigated for depositing the Al-Mo alloy onto the graphite fibers. The hollow cathode process for applying the alloy resulted in uniform coating of the fibers; however, the Mo concentrations in the coatings were low and curling of the fibers made handling difficult. The planar cathode process resulted in

slightly less uniform coating of the fibers, but an Al-17Mo coating was easily produced and fibers coated with this process were easy to handle. A micrograph one of the fibers coated using the planar cathode process is presented in Figure 4.

Fig. 3: Galvanic Current as a function of time for commercially pure Al and Al-18 Mo Alloys (as-deposited and heat treated) coupled to P75 graphite fibers in quiescent 0.1M NaCl, (at a pH of 8 and a temperature of 25° C). (Since the anodic area was 1 cm² the galvanic current equals the galvanic current density.)

Anodic polarization of a single coated fiber revealed a pitting potential of approximately -250 mV vs. SCE resulting in a passive range about half the size of the one obtained for the Al-18a/o Mo when it was deposited onto a Si substrate using the laboratory deposition system. The difference in polarization behavior was attributed to the columnar morphology of the Cordec Al-Mo deposit. While the polarization behavior of the single coated fibers was not nearly as good as the behavior of the alloy deposited onto Si, it was thought that this modest enhancement in corrosion resistance would be adequate enough and that consolidation of the alloy might result in further densification of the coating.

Composite Consolidation and Testing

Consolidation trials (via hot pressing) were conducted on the Al-17Mo alloy coated fibers at both Martin Marietta and Cordec Incorporated. For each consolidation trial, the preforms were created by unidirectional orientation of the coated fibers between Al interlayers and Al surface foils. The best consolidation was achieved on the Cordec specimen hot pressed at 550° C at a pressure of 8 ksi for 240 minutes.

Metallographic examination of the best Cordec composite revealed the presence of approximately 9 volume percent porosity and exposed graphite fibers at the composite surface. X-ray diffraction of the consolidated composite revealed the presence of precipitates. While the presence of precipitates was undesirable, it was not surprising in light of the higher than anticipated temperature needed for consolidation.

Fig. 4: Cross section of an Al-17 a/o Mo Alloy-Coated Graphite Fiber. The fiber was produced using a planar cathode sputtering system at Cordec Incorporated.

Fig. 5: Representative cross-sectional microstructures of corrosion resistant Al-14Mo/P120 Gr fiber composite.

Fig. 6: SEM micrograph of composite after polarization in 0.1M NaCl revealing lack of consolidation of coated fibers

Anodic polarization experiments were conducted on the composite panels that were considered to have consolidated relatively well. Unfortunately, none of the polarization curves generated on the composite specimens in chloride-containing environments showed evidence of passive behavior. The poor anodic polarization performance of the alloy was not unexpected considering that the composite contained galvanic couples between pure Al, the Al-17Mo alloy, and the graphite fibers. In addition, SEM inspection of the composite after corrosion testing, Figure 6, clearly revealed that diffusion bonding of the coated fibers was far from complete. In fact, the alloy coating on the fiber surfaces appeared to have undergone little or no change during either the diffusion bonding process or potentiodynamic polarization.

SUMMARY

This research has clearly revealed that nonequilibrium Al-Mo, Al-W, Al-Ta, Al-Cr alloys exhibit significantly enhanced resistance to corrosion when compared to pure Al or any commercial aluminum alloy. For two of the alloys investigated in this program (the intermediate solute concentration Al-Mo and Al-W alloys) this significantly enhanced corrosion resistance was maintained at nominal composite consolidation temperatures (400°C). In addition to anodic potentiodynamic polarization testing, the enhanced corrosion resistance of these alloys was confirmed in long-term galvanic coupling experiments. Precipitation reactions in the intermediate solute concentration Al-Mo and Al-W alloys were retarded as a result of the nanocrystalline /amorphous nature of these sputter deposited alloys.

Commercial deposition of an Al-17Mo alloy on P120 graphite fibers yielded a very columnar deposit that maintained a degree of flexibility similar to that of the uncoated fibers. The breakdown potential for the Al-17Mo coated fiber was several hundred millivolts greater than that of pure Al (or any commercial Al alloy), but it was also several hundred millivolts less than that of the Al-18Mo alloy sputtered on planar substrates using a laboratory scale system at Martin Marietta. This difference in performance between the alloy deposited by Cordec on graphite fibers and the alloy deposited by Martin Marietta on planar substrates was a result of the morphology differences between the two deposits. The alloy film produced at Martin Marietta was smooth and dense; whereas, the Cordec deposit was rough and columnar. Rough columnar deposits, such as the one illustrated in Figure 4 for the Al-17Mo alloy on the P120 graphite fibers, have been shown to significantly degrade localized corrosion resistance [31]. Fortunately, the morphology of the deposit can be changed by optimizing the sputtering conditions. In this research, optimization of the sputtering process was not conducted because of the limited budget and because it was hoped that hot pressing would densify the alloy.

Consolidation of the alloy via hot pressing proved to be a more difficult task than anticipated. As a result of the relatively high melting temperature of the alloy (715° C), consolidation was far from complete at the temperature and pressure ranges available for hot pressing. Void concentrations greater than 9 volume %, lack of diffusion bonding of the alloy coated fiber within the composite, and the presence of pure aluminum surface foils and inter-layers all contributed to the poor corrosion performance of the hot-pressed composite. SEM examination of the composite after anodic polarization testing confirmed that diffusion bonding of the coated fibers was far from complete. In addition, this analysis revealed that little or no degradation of the coated fibers had taken place; instead, corrosion of the composite was confined to the Al surface foils and interlayers. As a result of the excellent corrosion behavior of the nonequilibrium Al-17 Mo matrix alloy under these conditions (despite its less than optimal morphology), it is believed that corrosion resistant graphite-reinforced composites could be produced with this alloy via hot-isostatic pressing (HIPing). To insure that the enhanced corrosion resistance of the nonequilibrium Al alloy is not compromised by corrosion of the pure Al surface foils or interlayers these composites should either be HIPed without surface foils or HIPed with vapor deposited Al-17 Mo surface foils.

CONCLUSIONS

- 1) Aluminum alloyed with W or Mo at atomic concentrations between 10 and 25 percent showed the best overall corrosion resistance of the alloys investigated in this program. This enhanced corrosion resistance was maintained after heat-treatment at nominal composite consolidation temperatures (400° C).

- 2) The most promising alloys for use in MMCs exhibited amorphous or short range ordering.
- 3) Intermediate concentration Al-Mo alloys (with Mo concentration between 11 and 18 at/o %) provide the best combination of corrosion resistance, thermal stability, and alloy density for use as a matrix metal in graphite reinforced composites.
- 4) Consolidation of the nonequilibrium Al-17 Mo coated wires will require higher pressures than those used in this study.
- 5) Production of a corrosion resistant graphite reinforced composite utilizing nonequilibrium Al-Mo alloys will require processing without surface foils and inter-layers or with vapor deposited surface foils and inter-layers of the same composition as the matrix alloy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the Office of Naval Research (Dr. A.J. Sedriks) for their support of this research.

REFERENCES

1. Evans, J.M. and D.M. Braddick, *Corros. Sci.*, 1971, vol. 11, pp. 611-614.
2. Dull, D.L., W.C. Harrigan Jr., and M.F. Amateau, *Proceedings of Tri-service Corrosion of Military Equipment Conference*, F.H. Meyer, ed., Air Force Materials Laboratory Report AFML-TR-75-42, 1975, vol. 1, p. 399.
3. Crowe, C.R., Localized Corrosion Currents from Graphite Aluminum and Welded SiC/Al metal Matrix Composites, NRL Memorandum report 5415, Naval Research Laboratory, February, 1985.
4. Payer, J.H. and P.G. Sullivan, *Bicentennial of Materials*, Society for the Advancement of Material and Process Engineering, Azusa, CA, 1976 vol. 8, pp. 343-352.
5. Aylor, D.M. and R.M. Kain, ASTM STP 864 - Recent Advances in Composites in the US and Japan, Vinson and Taya, ed., American Society of Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, PA, 1985, pp. 632-647.
6. Trzaskoma, P.P., *Environmental Effects on Advanced Materials*, R.H. Jones and R.E. Ricker, ed., The Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society, Warrendale, PA, 1991, pp. 249-266.
7. Pfeifer, W.H. and W.J. Renton, ed., *American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics*, New York, NY, 1977, pp. 231-252.
8. Vassilaros, M.G., D.A. Davis, G.L. Steckel, and J.P. Gudas, *Proceeding of the 1980 Tri-Service Corrosion Conference*, vol. 2, U.S. Government Publication, 1980.
9. Aylor, D.M., R.J. Ferrara, and R.M. Kain, *Mater. Performance*, 1984, vol. 23, pp. 32-39.

10. Aylor, D.M. and P.J. Moran, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1985, vol. 132, pp. 1277-2684.
11. Kendall, E.G. and D.L. Dull, National Technical Information Service, U.S. Department of Commerce, AD-777, p. 160, (1974).
12. Buonanno, M.A., R.M. Latanision, L.H. Hihara, and J.F. Chiang, Environmental Effects on Advanced Materials, R.H. Jones and R.E. Ricker, ed., The Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society, Warrendale, PA, 1991, pp. 267-282.
13. Hihara, L.H., Corrosion of Aluminum-Matrix Composites, Ph.D. Dissertation, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, (1985).
14. Hihara L.H. and R.M. Latanision, *Mater. Sci. Engineering A*, 1990, vol. 126, pp. 231-234.
15. Hihara L.H. and R.M. Latanison, *Corrosion*, 1991, vol. 47, pp. 335-340.
16. Hihara L.H. and R.M. Latanison, *Corrosion*, 1992, vol. 48, pp. 546-552.
17. Harrigan, W.C. and R.H. Flowers, Failure Modes in Composites IV, J.A. Cornie and F.W. Crossman, eds., The Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society, Warrendale, PA, 1977, pp. 319-335.
18. Toth, I.J., W.D. Brenthall, and G.D. Menke, Composites: State of the Art, J.W. Weeton and E. Scala, eds., The Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society, Warrendale, PA, 1971, pp. 139-207.
19. Meyerer, W., D. Kizer, S. Paprocki, Failure Modes in Composites IV, J.A. Cornie and F.W. Crossman, ed., The Minerals, Metals, and Materials Society, Warrendale, PA, 1977, pp. 319-335.
20. Amateau, M.F., *J. Composite Mat.*, 1976, vol. 10, pp 279-296.
21. Nardone, V.C. and J.R. Strife, United Technologies Research Center, Interim Report R89-917711-4, East Hartford, CT, July 1989.
22. Weimer, R.J., W.F. Henshaw, T.G. Casswell, B.D. Dickerson, J.P. Hickerson, and S.D. Shelton, Fabrication of Thin-Walled Seamless Tubes from Gr/Mg Precursor Tapes, Cordec Corporation, Lorton, VA, 1992.
23. Pepper, R.T. and R.A. Penty, *J. Composite Mat.*, 1974, vol. 8, pp. 29-37.
24. Baker, A.A., C. Shipman, and P.W. Jackson, *Fibre Science and Technology*, 1972, vol. 5, pp. 213-218.
25. Shorshorov, M.Kh., T.A. Chernyshova, and L.I. Kobeleva, ICCM-IV, T. Hayashi, K. Kawata, and S Umekawa, ed., Toyoka, 1982, pp. 1273-1279.
26. Arsenault, R.J. and C.S. Pande, *Scripta Metallurgica*, 1984, vol. 18, pp. 1131-1134.
27. Baker, S.J. and W. Bonfield, *J. of Mater. Sci.*, 1978, vol. 13, pp. 1329-1334.

28. Fu, L.-J., M. Schmerling, and H.L. Marcus, *Composite Materials: Fracture and Fatigue*, ASTM Special Publication 907, H.T. Hahn, ed., 1984, pp. 51-72.
29. Khan, I.H., *Metallurgical Transactions A*, 1976, vol. 7A, pp. 1281-1289.
30. Harrigan Jr., W.C., *Metallurgical Transactions A*, 1978, vol. 9A.
31. Gunier, A., *X-Ray Diffraction In Crystals, Imperfect Crystals and Amorphous Bodies*, W.H. Freeman and Company, San Francisco, CA, 1963, pp. 121-126.